
MONITORING FRAMEWORK / RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Monitoring and Updating System for the Study of the Mechanism of Forced Expulsion through “Release”

Methodological Framework
for Monitoring, Verification and Updating the Research
on the Mechanism of Forced Expulsion through “Release”.

Version 1.1 - Minor update:
reference to UN Human Rights Council report A/HRC/61/57 added

Document status:
Methodological Framework for Monitoring and Updating the Research

Document purpose:
Establishing a systematic framework for monitoring, documenting and updating the research on the mechanism of forced expulsion through “release”, including the identification of new cases, verification of available information and the continuous refinement of the analytical and legal framework of the study.

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Position within the Research Series

This document forms part of a research series dedicated to the study of the mechanism of forced expulsion through “release.”

Documents in the Research Series

1. Analytical Report

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18444848

2. Concept Paper

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18643260

3. Methodological Glossary

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18717482

4. Definition Paper

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18734923

5. Methodological Framework

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18825890

6. Normative Legal Qualification

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18928282

The documents are interconnected and collectively form a unified conceptual and methodological framework.

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1. Purpose of the Monitoring System

This document establishes a system for monitoring and updating the research on the mechanism of forced expulsion through “release”.

The conducted research has shown that in a number of cases the release of political prisoners was accompanied by their subsequent forced expulsion beyond the territory of the state. In such situations, individuals were extracted from penitentiary institutions, escorted by state authorities to the border and expelled outside the territory of the country.

A characteristic feature of such cases is the absence of a real possibility for the released individual to refuse to leave the territory of the country. Refusal to leave the country effectively entails the return of the individual under the control of state authorities, including the possibility of repeated placement in conditions of isolation.

An additional feature of these cases is the absence of a legally formalized completion of the individual’s criminal-law status at the moment of their actual expulsion. In a number of documented episodes, the expulsion was also accompanied by the absence of documents necessary for the lawful crossing of the state border.

The combination of these circumstances distinguishes this mechanism from ordinary cases of release from places of detention and requires separate analytical and legal examination.

The identified practice may have a repetitive character. Therefore, the study of this mechanism is not considered complete and requires further observation.

The purpose of this document is to define the procedure for recording new cases and to establish the rules for updating the research.

2. Methodological Basis

The monitoring system is based on previously published research documents.

These include:

- the analytical report on the mechanism of forced expulsion through “release”;
- the conceptual description of this mechanism;
- the glossary of key terms;
- the criteria for the identification of cases of forced expulsion;
- the normative legal qualification of the mechanism within the framework of international law.

These documents form a unified analytical and methodological foundation of the research. The monitoring system does not introduce a new methodology. It is based on the analytical framework formulated in the author’s previously published studies and applies it to the analysis of new cases. Such an approach ensures the consistency of the research and the comparability of the data obtained.

3. Object of Monitoring

Within the framework of the monitoring system, new cases of the application of the mechanism of forced expulsion through “release” are recorded. Cases whose compliance with the established criteria requires additional verification are also subject to analysis.

The task of the monitoring system is the recording of new cases and the clarification of the practice of application of this mechanism.

Such cases include situations in which:

- individuals are extracted from penitentiary institutions;
- released individuals are escorted by state authorities to the state border;
- expulsion is carried out without documents necessary for the lawful crossing of the border;

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- refusal to leave the territory of the state entails the return of the individual under the control of state authorities;
 - expulsion is carried out without a legally formalized completion of the individual's criminal-law status.

4. Sources of Information

Various types of information sources are used for the documentation of cases.

Such sources may include:

- testimonies of released political prisoners;
- testimonies of relatives and close associates;
- publications of mass media;
- materials of human rights organizations;
- official statements of state authorities;
- video recordings and photographic materials;
- other documentary sources.

Whenever possible, information is verified through several independent sources. This allows for increasing the accuracy and reliability of the recorded facts.

5. Verification and Qualification of Cases

Each documented case is analyzed on the basis of the identification criteria developed within the framework of the research on the mechanism of forced expulsion through "release".

A case may be qualified as part of this mechanism when its key elements are confirmed.

Such elements include:

- extraction of the individual from a penitentiary institution;
- absence of a legally formalized completion of the individual's criminal-law status;
- transfer of the individual under the control of state authorities to the border;
- absence of a real possibility to refuse to leave the territory of the state;
- uncertainty of the individual's legal status after expulsion.

The presence of the combination of these elements makes it possible to qualify the respective case as a manifestation of the mechanism of forced expulsion through "release".

The application of uniform criteria ensures the consistency of the analysis and prevents arbitrary interpretation of individual cases.

6. Updating the Research

The monitoring system provides for the possibility of regular updates of the research.

As new confirmed cases emerge, updated versions of the analytical report or additional materials may be published.

Such updates may include:

- newly documented cases;
- clarification of the structure of the mechanism;
- description of changes in the practice of its application.

To indicate updates, a versioning system may be used, for example:

Version 1.0 - initial analytical report

Version 1.1 - update based on new cases

Version 1.2 - subsequent update

Such a system makes it possible to track the development of the mechanism and to maintain transparency of the research.

7. Continuation of the Research

The monitoring system makes the research on the mechanism of forced expulsion through “release” open for further development.

As new data emerge, the empirical basis of the research may expand, and the analytical model may be refined.

The recording of new cases makes it possible to track changes in the application of this mechanism and to maintain the relevance of its legal and analytical assessment.

Thus, the research is considered as an ongoing analytical process aimed at the systematic documentation and analysis of cases of the application of this mechanism.

This document is part of a series of analytical studies dedicated to the identification, description and legal qualification of the mechanism of forced expulsion through “release”. All documents in the series form a unified research system and are subject to further updates as new empirical data become available.

This document is part of the research series “Forced Expulsion through ‘Release’.”

The analytical framework presented in this research series was developed prior to the publication of the report of the United Nations Human Rights Council Group of Independent Experts on the Situation of Human Rights in Belarus (A/HRC/61/57, 2026). The report refers to individuals who have “fled or were forcefully expelled from Belarus”. While the report documents this phenomenon in the broader context of repression, the present research series provides a distinct analytical interpretation by conceptualizing it as a specific mechanism of forced expulsion through “release” from detention.¹

¹ United Nations Human Rights Council (2026).
Report of the Group of Independent Experts on the Situation of Human Rights in Belarus.
A/HRC/61/57.
https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/documents/hrbodies/hrcouncil/sessions-regular/session61/A_HRC_61_57.pdf
